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Neonatal seizure detection algorithms: The effect of channel count

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Abstract: The number of electrodes used to acquire neonatal EEG signals varies between institutions. Therefore, tools for automatic EEG analysis, such as neonatal seizure detection algorithms, need to be able to handle different electrode montages in order to find widespread use. The aim of this study was to analyse the effect of montage on neonatal seizure detector performance. A full 18-channel montage was compared to reduced 3- and 8-channel montages using a convolutional neural network for seizure detection. Sensitivity decreased by 10 – 18 % for the reduced montages while specificity was mostly unaffected. Electrode artefacts and artefacts associated with biological rhythms caused incorrect classification of non-seizure activity in some cases, but these artefacts were filtered out in the 3-channel montage. Other types of artefacts had little effect. Reduced montages result in some reduction in classifier accuracy, but the performance may still be acceptable. Recording artefacts had a limited effect on detection accuracy.

Keywords: Seizure detection, neonatal EEG, reduced montage

1 Introduction

A neonatal electroencephalogram (EEG) is used for continuous monitoring of the state of the brain and for making patient prognosis [1]. Monitoring is usually done by placing 2 – 12 electrodes on the scalp and measuring voltage difference across electrodes [2]. The signals are frequently visualized and processed as bipolar derivations (channels), the set of which is called a *montage*. In [3, 4] it was shown that a full 19-electrode setup (18-channels) enabled detection of a larger number of seizures compared to a reduced montage, however a reduced montage may still produce clinically useful information. Fewer electrodes are preferred in practice since such setups can be applied more quickly and are easier to maintain for the duration of the recordings, some of which may last several days.

Due to scarcity of neonatal EEG experts [5] and time consuming analysis, there is an interest in developing tools for

automatic EEG analysis. Such tools could make the analysis faster, more accessible, prompt wider use of EEG in NICUs, and eventually lead to improved patient care. In order for those tools to find widespread use, they need to be able to handle a variable number of EEG channels since recording protocols differ between institutions.

In this study the effects of using 3- and 8-channels in a neonatal seizure detection algorithm (NSDA) were analysed by comparing them to a full 18-channel montage. The effects of artefacts on NSDA accuracy were also investigated.

2 Methods

A publicly available EEG data set [6] containing 18-channel EEG recordings from 79 neonates and seizure annotations (labeling) by three human experts was used in this study. This data set has been studied in the context of NSDAs in the past [7–10]. The annotations do not specify which channels contain seizures, only that a seizure is present in one or more of the channels. Therefore an additional set of channel-by-channel seizure annotations made by a fourth annotator [11] was also used. This second set of annotations was only used to analyse the location of (un)detected seizures with respect to the reduced 3- and 8-channel montages. Channel-by-channel artefact annotations of the same data were obtained from [12]. The artefact annotations span approx. 36 % of the recordings and are divided into six categories: clean EEG, device interference artefacts, electromyography (EMG) artefacts, movement artefacts, electrode artefacts and artefacts associated with non-cortical biological (cardiac or respiratory) rhythms. These annotations were used to analyse which types of artefacts may cause incorrect classifications. Only segments belonging to one of the six categories were used for the artefact analysis.

Following [7], each EEG recording was band-pass filtered (0.5 – 16 Hz), down-sampled to 32 Hz and cut into 16 s long segments with 12 s overlap. Individual segments were standardised so that the mean was zero and the standard deviation was one. Three montages were used in this study, an 18-channel montage (figure 1), an 8-channel montage (Fp1-T3, T3-O1, Fp1-C3, C3-O1, Fp2-C4, C4-O2, Fp2-T4, T4-O2) and a 3-channel montage (F3-P3, F4-P4 and F3-F4).

The seizure detector was a convolutional neural network [13] combined with an attention layer [10] to handle a

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Fig. 1: Full 18-channel (double banana) montage. Electrodes are positioned according to the 10-20 system.

variable number of channels during the training and testing (i.e. when classifications/predictions are made) as described in [7]. The NSDA was trained in a leave-one-subject-out cross-validation setting. The training set contained an equal number of consensus seizure and non-seizure segments (segments where all experts were in agreement). To determine seizure/non-seizure segments, the human expert labels were used instead of the channel-by-channel labels. The network weights were optimised using the Adam optimiser with an initial learning rate of 0.001 and halving the learning rate every 10 epochs. Learning was done with a mini-batch of size 128 and stopped after 30 epochs [7]. The area under curve, sensitivity and specificity were used to evaluate classifier performance. Following [8, 9], predictions from the left-out subjects were concatenated into a single array and compared to consensus labels. By concatenating predictions, it was possible to use data from all the recordings, including those that do not contain any seizures.

3 Results

The influence of montage on detector performance was analysed by training and testing on all of the three montages. In all cases the labels correspond to the scoring done by the three experts who utilized the 18-channel montage. As most neonatal seizures are partial, i.e. they affect only a small part of the brain [14], they appear only in a subset of channels of the full 18-channel montage. Therefore, some seizures may not be picked up by the 3- or 8-channel montages and a choice of the montage is expected to influence the training and the classification of the NSDA.

As expected, for all training montages, sensitivity increased with an increasing number of channels in the test set (table 1). For the 3- and 8-channel montages, some seizure segments were incorrectly classified as non-seizures, since the

seizure activity was not picked up by the montage. This is further illustrated in figures 2A and 2B which include the seizure segments picked up by the 3- and 8-channel montages. The detector performance on such segments is comparable to the 18-channel montage, especially for detectors with clinically useful specificity (defined here as 95 % or above). On the rest of the segments (figures 2C and 2D) the performance drops noticeably in comparison to the 18-channel montage.

Tab. 1: Comparison of the area under the curve (AUC), sensitivity (SE), and specificity (SP) values for 3-, 8- and 18-channel montages used for training and testing. Metrics were calculated on concatenated recordings. All the data was used, irrespective of seizure and artefact annotation.

		Testing montage		
		A: 3-channel		
Training montage	AUC	SE [%]	SP [%]	
3-channel	0.90	77	91	
8-channel	0.89	72	92	
18-channel	0.90	69	95	
		B: 8-channel		
		AUC	SE [%]	SP [%]
3-channel	0.89	81	87	
8-channel	0.90	78	91	
18-channel	0.89	77	93	
		C: 18-channel		
		AUC	SE [%]	SP [%]
3-channel	0.92	86	85	
8-channel	0.92	85	89	
18-channel	0.94	87	93	

Table 1C shows that using the 18-channel montage for training resulted in an NSDA with the highest performance accuracy when the detector was tested using 18 channels. There are two key differences with respect to the other two training montages. First, the 18-channel montage has more data for training than the 3- and 8-channel montages since each channel carries information used in training the NSDA. Second, the data was annotated using the 18-channel montage and therefore some seizure activity was not picked up by the 3- and 8-channel montages. This led to incorrectly labelled training segments and likely contributed to a decrease in specificity [15].

Moreover, a marginal increase in specificity with decreasing number of channels used in the test set is observed. In [12] it was shown that the 3-channel montage is less susceptible to artefacts than the other two. We therefore investigated whether artefact contamination leads to an increase in incorrectly classified segments.

Fig. 2: Panels A and B include seizure segments picked up by the 3- and 8-channel montages. Panels C and D include the remaining seizure segments. N_S denotes the number of seizure segments. All consensus non-seizure segments were included, irrespective of artefact annotation. The horizontal line represents a lower bound for clinically useful specificity (95 %). In all cases the NSDA was trained using the 18-channel montage.

Table 2 shows sensitivity and specificity values for both the clean segments and the segments with artefacts. Only channels annotated as clean or containing an artefact were used as inputs to the NSDA (a subset of the 18-channel montage). For the seizure segments, a seizure annotation on the corresponding channels was required since it is unreasonable to expect a seizure prediction when seizure activity is absent in the input. Due to the limited number of seizure segments with an artefact and seizure annotation on the same channels, it is difficult to draw definite conclusions. The specificity values show that the NSDA performs similarly on clean inputs as for inputs containing device, EMG or movement artefacts. A 5 – 10 % lower accuracy was obtained for segments containing electrode and biological rhythm artefacts. Overall, with the exception of electrode and biological rhythm artefacts, artefacts have a minor effect on the NSDA. A likely explanation is that a relatively large number of artefacts is included in the training set (approx. 30 % [12]).

A comparison of segments containing artefacts and segments with a clean annotation on all channels is provided in figure 3. A marginal difference is observed for the 8- and 18-channel montages in the clinically significant region whereas the 3-channel montage appears to be less affected by artefacts. This could be due to the fact that F3/F4 and P3/P4 electrodes

Tab. 2: Sensitivity and specificity using only a subset of the 18-channel montage annotated as clean or containing an artefact. The seizure segments correspond to the seizure channel-by-channel annotation. Number of segments for each case are inside parentheses. The NSDA was trained using the 18-channel montage.

	Sensitivity [%]	Specificity [%]
Clean	81 (108)	95 (17121)
Device interference	67 (3)	95 (1552)
EMG	70 (56)	96 (14630)
Movement	100 (11)	96 (4225)
Electrode artefact	73 (26)	89 (3979)
Biological rhythm	100 (10)	84 (1747)

are in general less sensitive to artefacts than the prefrontal and temporal electrodes which are included in the other montages [12]. It should be noted however that these observations are based on a limited amount of data.

4 Conclusion

Training an NSDA on a reduced montage resulted in a detector with a lower classification accuracy compared to a classifier trained on the full montage. This can be attributed to incorrectly labelled segments and a smaller training set. Furthermore, testing the NSDA on a reduced montage led to a lower but still clinically useful seizure detection rate. This is in line with studies analysing the effect of the number of channels on scoring by human experts [3, 4, 16–18]. Finally, the effects of artefacts on classification accuracy were investigated. We conclude that the majority artefacts appear to have only a small effect. Electrode artefacts and artefacts associated with biological rhythms caused some non-seizure segments to be incorrectly classified as seizure segments. These may in some instances be avoided by using the 3-channel montage. However, future studies with more data are required to confirm the observations.

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Fig. 3: Specificity as a function of sensitivity for 3-, 8- and 18-channel montages. The dashed lines represent 2525 non-seizure segments annotated as clean and the solid lines represent 23734 non-seizure segments where one or more channels contained an artefact. Seizure segments picked up by each montage were used to calculate sensitivity. The horizontal line represents a lower bound for clinically useful specificity (95 %). In all cases the NSDA was trained using the 18-channel montage.

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